

Deliverable D4.3

Validated instructions, Standard Operating Procedures and protocols for use in the supply chain

DATE: 29 NOVEMBER, 2024

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D4.3

Funded by the
European Union

General Information

Call identifier:	HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-10
GA Number:	101060712
Start date of project:	01/06/2022
Work Package:	WP4
Type:	Deliverable
Number:	D4.3
Version:	1
Due Date:	30/11/2024
Submission date:	29/11/2024
Responsible organisation:	University of Florence, UNIFI
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Dissemination Level:	Public

Document Type		
PRO	Technical/economic progress report (internal work package reports indicating work status)	
DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	X
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

Dissemination Level		
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PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
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1. Executive Summary

The main goal of the WP4 is to develop a comprehensive suite of tools for metagenomic, genetic, and stable isotope approaches to determine and ensure the quality, safety, and traceability of seafood products within the supply chain, which is essential to improve decision-making at various levels in the fish industry, and at the same time, increase consumer confidence in seafood. Traceability of seafood involves tracking both the geographical origin of seafood products and their production method (wild-caught or farmed), also to prevent fraud and guarantee the quality of fish products. In this report, contributions to Deliverable 4.3 (*Validated instructions, Standard Operating procedures, and protocols for use in the supply chain*) that comprehend the comparison of different technologies that will allow the cost-benefits of these platforms at different levels of decision-making in the fish industry to be assessed.

In this report, different technologies, including sensors for product freshness, microbiological traceability tools, and genetic markers, are going to be discussed. Some of the results here provided have been reported in D4.2 since they are unavoidable to report cost-benefits and discuss synergies between methods provided.

2. Freshness sensors and freshness experiment with targeted sequencing

2.1 Freshness sensors developed by UMF

The UMF team has developed two strategies for the detection of bacteria or biomarkers of biofilm formation and bacterial contamination:

- i) electrochemical sensors for the detection of electroactive molecules, serving as biomarkers of biofilm formation or bacteria contamination using SPEs modified with nanomaterials
 - Biofilm detection using an electrochemical sensor (Figure 1) for the detection of cyclic diguanosine-monophosphate (cdGMP), a molecule secreted by different bacteria during the process of biofilm formation
 - *P. aeruginosa* detection using an electrochemical sensor for PQS, a molecule involved in the quorum sensing in *P. aeruginosa*
- (ii) electrochemical aptasensors, using aptamers specific to a bacterium or to quorum sensing molecule characteristic of Gram-negative bacteria
 - Aptasensor for the detection of *Salmonella enterica typhimurium* (Figure 2), using a whole-cell aptamer specific for *Salmonella enterica typhimurium*
 - Detection of Gram-negative bacteria using an electrochemical aptasensor for 3-O-C12-HSL, a molecule involved in quorum sensing

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the sensor for cdGMP detection

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the developed AuNP-based electrochemical aptasensor

The electrochemical sensors present several advantages:

- rapid analysis (analysis time in the range of minutes)
- simple protocols (no need for specialized personnel)
- good selectivity (assured by bioelements (e.g. aptamers) or biomimetic elements (molecularly imprinted polymers))
- good sensitivity (assured by electrochemical methods (e.g. differential pulse voltammetry) and electrode modification with nanomaterials (e.g. gold nanoparticles, graphene, carbon nanotubes))
- miniaturization (need of small sample volumes (smaller than 0.1 mL))
- portability (on field analysis using small, portable potentiostat and screen printed electrodes (SPEs) (Figure 3))
- low cost (cheap apparatus (portable potentiostats cheaper than 1000 Euro) and single-use SPEs (cheaper than 3 euro))
- versatility (the electrodes can be modified with different biorecognition elements – aptamers specific for different bacterial species are commercially available or can be obtained through SELEX (Systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment) procedure.

The electrochemical sensors present some limitations, too:

- lower sensitivity for simple, on field analysis
- difficulties for simultaneous detection of several bacteria; this can be corrected by the development of a battery of sensors, each being specific for a certain bacterium

The results of DNA microbiome analysis can be used in a follow up project for the development of electrochemical sensors in two directions:

- development of electrochemical aptasensors, each specific for a certain bacterium using aptamers, commercially available or developed through SELEX
- development of electrochemical DNA sensors, with several examples of electrochemical DNA sensors being able to detect DNA segments specific for a certain bacterium (Wu et al., 2019)

Figure 3. Example of a portable potentiostat and SPE

2.2 Freshness experiment with targeted sequencing (UNIFI)

To evaluate microbial communities related to freshness, we set up an experiment using the protocol developed for traceability experiments. We collected individuals by a local wholesaler of *S.aurata* and *D. labrax*, we simulated supply chain/consumer conditions, storing whole fish at 4°C, and we collected every day for three days a gill sample from each fish. In addition, we performed everyday simultaneously to the sampling the *Quality Index Method (QIM)* (Table 1), assigning a spoilage score to each fish at the exact time of sampling, to correlate specific microbial signatures to specific spoilage states.

Table 1. Quality Index Method (QIM) Table, developed and adapted by Larsen et al. (1992)

Quality parameter	Character	Score (ice/seawater)
General Appearance	Skin	0 Bright, Shining
		1 Bright
		2 Dull
	Bloodspot on gill cover	0 None
		1 Small, 10-30%
		2 Big, 30-50%
		3 Very Big, 50-100%
	Stiffness	0 Stiff, in rigor mortis
		1 Elastic
		2 Firm
		3 Soft
	Belly	0 Firm
		1 Belly burst
	Smell	0 Fresh, seaweed/metallic
		1 Neutral
		2 Musty/sour
		3 Stale meat/rancid
Eyes	Clarity	0 Clear
		1 Cloudy
	Shape	0 Normal
		1 Plain
		2 Sunken
Gills	Colour	0 Characteristic, red
		1 Faded, discolored
	Smell	0 Fresh, seaweed/metallic
		1 Neutral
		2 Sweaty/slightly rancid
		3 Sour stink/stale rancid
Sum of scores		(Min. 0 and Max. 20)

For the analysis of samples, we followed the same protocol described in D4.2. We collected two kinds of samples for each individual: a gill biopsy and a gill swab (obtained by swabbing the whole gill). This was done to assess if there are any relevant differences between the two sampling methods and to select the easiest but effective method. The methodology used for sequencing is the same as depicted above for the traceability experiment. Results are depicted in Figure 4, showing a bar plot of the main bacterial genera associated with seabass and seabream, for both sampling matrices. This data shows that swabs and gill biopsies give similar results. According to this, gill swabbing, for the easier obtaining method, should be proposed as a standard method of sampling fish specimens for freshness detection.

Microbial biodiversity serves as a crucial indicator of freshness. In our experiments, a diverse microbial population often indicates freshness, as spoilage microbes have not yet dominated. In our case study, the gills of *Dicentrarchus labrax* and *Sparus aurata*, show rich microbial communities after fishing denoting freshness and quality, whereas a reduction in biodiversity is a sign of spoilage, or longer shelf-life.

Figure 4. Relative abundances at Genus level of microbial taxa. The bar graphs represent the main taxonomic classes associated with the gills and the gill swabs of sea bass and sea bream. Taxonomic assignments at the genus level are shown in the legend following the color code.

Microbial data from gills' swabs were used to investigate spoilage-related microbial changes. All of the used indices showed that the spoilage process influences deeply the microbial community composition. As also shown in Figure 5, there is a complete dominance of a few taxa over the others, with time, resulting in a fast decrease in diversity values (Figure 5).

To determine which ASVs were statistically increasing or decreasing over time, we performed a differential abundance analysis. This method found 42 ASVs that decrease and 19 ASVs which increased in abundance with fish spoilage.

Taxonomical allocation of the two groups of ASVs was done at the genus level. The group showing a significant decrease at the time point 2 was mainly composed of the genera *Shewanella*, *Psychrobacter*, *Flavobacterium*, *Candidatus Branchiomonas*, and *Bizonia*. The ASVs that took advantage of fish spoilage were assigned to the genera *Photobacterium*, *Shewanella*, *Moritella*, *Cetobacterium*, and *Aliivibrio* (Figure 6). Most of the latter genera (*Photobacterium*, *Shewanella*, *Moritella*) are already identified as spoilage-specific organisms (Boziaris, I. S., & Parlapani, F. F. (2017).

Interestingly, ASVs belonging to the genus *Shewanella* were found both increasing and decreasing over time. This is probably because they belong to two different species, and at this moment of the analysis, they cannot be distinguished.

Figure 5. Diversity indices change with spoilage. The boxplots show the values (y axis) of 7 different diversity indices at the three time points (x axis).

Figure 6. ASVs abundances change over-time. Barplots showing the abundance of the differentially distributed ASVs along the three time points. On the x axis are represented the samples, on the y axis the relative abundance of the ASVs. The plots are split horizontally based on the trend (on top the ASVs decreasing with spoilage, on the bottom the ones increasing) and vertically based on the time point.

Also in a synergy optic with UMF, an untargeted metagenomic sequencing has been carried out. The untargeted metagenomic sequencing allows to deepen the resolution of sequencing,

allowing to obtain bacterial taxa at the species level. This will improve drastically the possibility of obtaining specific primers for DNA detections with electrochemical DNA sensors.

3. Microbiological and genetic traceability tools (UNIFI, UNIPD)

3.1 Microbiological tool

As stated in deliverable 4.2, both microbiological and genetic methods showed a high efficiency in discriminating fish samples according to their origin and their method of production (wild-caught or farmed). Analysis of differential abundance allowed the detection of a set of ASVs (unique bacterial genera) that have been selected for primer development. The possibility of using these primers for rapid identification of bacterial markers through Real Time – PCR is currently being tested. A brief results summary is proposed.

From the analysis of microbial diversities, lower diversity values were obtained for cultured samples, with the exception of Malta, which showed values similar to the wild counterpart (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Alpha-diversity analysis results. The boxplots show the values of different diversity metrics (rows) in fishes from aquaculture (left) and from the wild (right).

Differences between microbial community structure were evaluated using Bray-Curtis distances. In the case of wild samples, differences between sampling sites were less consistent in comparison to samples from aquaculture, which resulted to be very distinct in the Non Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) plot (Figure 8).

To understand the taxa which are the most responsible for these differences, a differential abundance analysis was performed. Among the taxa with a significantly different distribution among sites, some were identified as markers for fish origin assessment.

As shown in Figure 9, the identified markers were capable of solving the cluster analysis of samples, and so of distinguishing across the different sampling sites.

Those markers are currently being used for the development of a rapid detection kit with RT-PCR, and also with the possibility to implement with UMF sensors, as stated in 2.2.

Figure 8. Beta-diversity analysis results. NMDS plots of wild (left) and cultured (right) fishes grouped by sampling site.

Figure 9. Marker ASVs. Heatmap showing the scaled and centered abundance of ASVs across samples and cluster analysis of samples based on ASVs distribution.

Cost/Benefit assessment:

Costs

Equipment: Require specialized equipment for DNA analysis (for example: Illumina MiSeq for targeted sequencing)

Operational cost: Low. Sample preparation from DNA extraction to amplification are part of standard protocols. Reagents are widely available and they are scalable (see Table 2 for specifics)

Training: Require specialized metagenomic trained personnel and bioinformatician

Benefits

Traceability and production method detection: The gill microbiota is subject to species-specific, ecological, and environmental variables, making it suitable for discrimination of both fished and farmed samples. It's scalable and capable of handling multiple samples simultaneously. Currently, the University of Florence is working on the development of a set of primers for Real-Time PCR that will allow an easy and quick discrimination between different origins, based on bacterial markers detected through targeted metagenomic analysis.

Operational costs for microbiome analysis

Below is an estimate of the targeted sequencing cost per sample using Illumina Miseq technology. The prices are related to the workflow reported in the SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) already submitted in deliverable D4.2 and shown in the Demonstration Session in FishEUTrust GA Meeting held in Olhao, in 6th November 2024. This workflow is a standard targeted sequencing procedure for environmental microbiota, according to Illumina Protocol, adapted for fish gills microbiota. The costs represent an estimate, as the price of reagents can vary widely depending on the suppliers. Still, it can be considered a reliable estimate based on a well-trodden and widely used protocol in the microbiology and metagenomics laboratory at the University of Florence. The costs will be addressed point to point according to SOPs, and various kits are also already reported in SOPs or standard kits suggested by Illumina Protocol. Minor and routine reagents and basic consumables are not reported, since they are part of all microbiology and molecular biology laboratories.

Table 2. Estimate of per sample for targeted metagenomic sequencing

Protocol	Reagent	Estimated Price per sample (in €)	Notes
Genomic DNA extraction	Powersoil Pro Kit	6-7	Considering 250 reactions kit
16S targeted amplification	Taq DNA Polymerase	0.30-1	Considering a 100 reactions kit
-	Specific Primers	0.10	
Library preparation	Indexes (Kit Nextera XT)	3-10	Considering a 96 indexes kit (in dual-indexing)(up to 384 samples)
-	Purification beads	1-3	
-	(Kapa Pure Beads)		
Sequencing	300 cycles kit (2x150 bp) (comprehending buffers, sequencing cartridge and flow cell)	10-12	Considering 100-130 samples per run
Total cost per sample		20-33	

3.2 Genetic tool

Genotyping by SNP array (UNIPD)

Genetic markers are a powerful tool to trace the geographic origin of unknown samples. The effectiveness and consistency of the genetic assignment depends on the number of markers available as well as from the number of reference samples. In the case of the seabream the complete genome sequenced in 2018 (Pauletto et al., 2018) and the identification of more than 25,000 SNPs allowed the development a SNP array suitable for sea bream population analysis (Panaloza et al., 2021). This array was demonstrated to be effective at detecting population structure across a wide range of fish populations from diverse geographical origins (Villanueva et al., 2022).

Within the FishEUTrust, we used the SNPs array described above on a sample set of wild and aquacultured sea bream obtained from Spain (CATEGA), Portugal (IPMA) and Malta (AquaBioTech). The purpose was to verify the ability of this genetic tool to differentiate the three populations sampled in the FishEUTrust project and identify the origin of each fish sample. The other goal was to test the possibility to assign back each fish to its population of origin.

From the three sites we obtained 30 individuals catch in the wild and 30 from local sea bream farms. In the case of Spain, the samples from cultivated fish were only 20, therefore the total number of fish samples analyzed by the SNP array was 170.

Results

Of the 170 DNA processed for SNPs profiling 9 of these did not reach the quality necessary for a reliable signal (M_A_19, M_A_25, M_A_26, P_W_21, P_W_22, P_W_24, P_W_25, P_W_26, S_A_9), therefore they were excluded and the analyses were referred to 161 individual SNP profile based on 27,913 common SNPs.

Population structure

In order to verify the existence of some genetic cluster among the 161 samples of *S. aurata* we applied a *Discriminant Analysis of Principal Components* (DAPC) by using *Adegenet 2.1.6*. (Jonbart and Collins, 2022). The results are reported in the graphic representation of Fig. 10. The SNPs profiles clearly distinguish the 6 sample groups (S_A, S_W, P_A, P_W, M_A, M_W) in 6 distinct clusters providing evidence of the ability of this genetic tool to discriminate groups.

Figure 10. DPCA on 161 sea bream sample based on 27,913 common SNPs. code: S_A=Spain aquaculture, S_W=Spain wild, P_A=Portugal aquaculture, P_W=Portugal wild, M_A=Malta aquaculture, M_W=Malta wild

Population assignment

We tested the possibility to assign with a certain probability an individual to its population/group of origin. To this end, we used the “AssignPOP” bioinformatic tool (Chen et al., 2018) that helps to perform population assignment using a machine-learning framework. It generates a SNPs reference baseline and then assign “unknown” samples (that were not part of the dataset used to generate the baseline) to one population with a certain probability. Our baseline consists of a dataset of 149 individuals from the 6 populations/groups (S_A, S_W, P_A, P_W, M_A, M_W) since 12 individuals (3 per each group) were excluded from baseline creation and used as “unknown” for posterior population assignment (see below). To evaluate the baseline, we tested 3 different classification machine-learning functions to build the predictive models (SVM, randomForest and naiveBayes).

Our unknown individuals (not included in the baseline dataset) were: M_A_1, M_A_9, M_A_27, M_W_1, M_W_6, M_W_18, P_A_1, P_A_11, P_A_27, P_W_1, P_W_14, P_W_29, S_A_1, S_A_14, S_A_24, S_W_1, S_W_8, S_W_15.

The result of individual assignment to one the identified populations and the associated posterior probability is reported in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. Assignment of “unknown” individuals to one population and associate posterior probability

All M_A, M_W, P_A and S_A individuals were correctly assigned to their origin population **with 100% probability**, whereas individuals P_W_1, S_W_1 and S_W_8 were miss-assigned. The possibility of using the larger dataset including the populations described in Villeneuve et al. (2022) for generating a wider baseline will be explored.

Here, we hypothesize a cost-benefit analysis of the two proposed methods for seafood traceability: microbiological and genetic. In particular, the methods proposed regard the analysis of fish gill microbiota through targeted metagenomic sequencing and SNP-based genetic analysis.

Cost/benefit Assessment

Costs

DNA extraction: this is a standard procedure that requires commercial kit, disposable plastics, reagents and instruments commonly used in molecular biology labs.

SNP array: once DNA (of good quality) is extracted from the target samples (seabream specimens, in this case) the SNP array analysis is commercially provided (it should be noted that, currently, only few companies offer this service).

Training: Whereas the wet lab part (DNA extraction) requires basic molecular biology competences, for the analyses of the SNP array outcome it is needed specialized personnel with good bioinformatic skills and a minimum of informatic resources.

Time laps for results acquisition. It takes not less than one month to obtain the SNP array results and from the DNA shipment. The elaboration of SNPs data takes a couple of days for population analysis and individual assignment.

Benefits

The completely sequenced seabream genome is the fundamental source of genetic markers from which has been designed the SNP array used in our analyses. This SNP array was based on more than 25,000 SNPs and tested on a large set of seabream populations from a very broad geographic range (Villanueva et al., 2022). This provide an extremely powerful tool that can reach 100% of probability of correct assignment provided that a good reference SNP baseline is existing.

Operational costs for genetic/genomic analysis based on SNP array

DNA extraction and quality check

- man/power: about 120hr to extract DNA from 170 seabream gills
- Chemicals and consumables (plastics etc.): 14.7€/sample
- SNP/Cheap: 26,0 €/sample – results are provided in about one month after DNA shipment to the company. It should be noted here that each SNP-array plate is set for the genotyping of 384 samples and cannot be reduced. Thus, having a lower number of individual genotyping (170) we have analyzed our sample in duplicate or triplicate.

4. Overall summary

Gill microbiota allows, with moderate expenses, to detect differences between samples according to geographical origin and production method. The results obtained allowed to produce a set of primers to further break down time-consuming procedures, and allowing to reduce the cost per sample. This set of primers will be further tested on a new set of samples to test its robustness. In addition, a possible synergy with UMF is currently under evaluation, based on bacterial markers (reported in Paragraph 2.1). This will be strengthened by the untargeted sequencing, that was conducted not only for the freshness experiment, but also for the tracking assessment. In principle our results could allow the development of rapid, cost effective and simple methods by transferring the results from metagenomic studies to potentiostat and SPE based sensors. As to the genetic tool using the SNP array technology, its final cost can be less than 50€ per samples (excluding labor cost) which is sufficiently low for such a powerful technology moreover it could be eventually combined with the microbiome tool (the statistical power of the combined tools is currently being under evaluation). However, these costs are SNP array are reduced/reasonable if the sample size is scaled-up to the order of hundreds, moreover it should be considered that it takes about one month after DNA extraction to obtain SNP array results.

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